

Original Research Article

Managerial Strategies for Students' Safety in the Aftermath of Covid-19 in Public Secondary Schools in Kogi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated managerial strategies for students' safety in post COVID-19 era in public secondary schools in Kogi State. The purpose was to ascertain the facilities required for students' safety, problems encountered in the procurement of safety facilities and strategies to be followed in the proper management of students' safety in public secondary schools in the aftermath of COVID-19. Based on quantitative research methodology, the study adopted purposive sampling. 214 public secondary school principals were selected through purposive sampling with the total enumeration technique. Students' safety in Post COVID-19 Questionnaire (SSPCQ) served as an instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected for the study and the outcome indicated that problems such as paucity of funds for the procurement of aids, reduction of students' enrolment, and shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space were problems encountered in the management of students' safety in post COVID-19 era by the school management in Kogi state.

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1. Introduction

Self-improvement through learning, information, abilities, and propensities across ages is gotten from training. The remarkable place of appropriate instruction for the social, financial, and moral advancement of nations cannot be sabotaged. It truly deserves note that the episode of the coronavirus (the COVID-19) plague has severely impacted

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the development of instruction at all levels. The coronavirus infection is a truly infectious sickness that has pained the total populace from December 2019 till right now. Information from Wikipedia and other researchers from a few hours on 18th August 2021 shows that the lethal illness spread out rapidly using beads (WHO, 2020a) and has upset north of 208 million victims which has about around fatalities worldwide. Thus, nations have carried out different defensive measures, including a series of visual and social removal steps to reduce the epidemiological bend and stay away from grimness and mortality brought about by COVID-19 (Barasa et al., 2020).

Preventive measures have been embraced by various nations to avert the spread of the epidemic in physical separation such as limitation of development and closing down of educational institutions and other public places (UNESCO, 2020). All levels of educational systems ranging from nursery to tertiary institutions have been affected by the pandemic (Lindzon, 2020) in Eze, Sefotho, Onyishi, and Eseadi (2021). Lindzon (2020) thought that the best way to hold individual well-being during the period was to shut down the schools to control the spread of the infection among schools and prevent a move to frail people. Eze et al (2021) have lamented that the rapid spread of the disease (coronavirus) and subsequent shutdown of the schools have negative impacts on the people who are supposed to make a terrible imprint on the essence of the schooling system. According to UNESCO (2020) and Nicola et al (2020), More than 188 out of 195 nations have been adhering to such measures overall which limit mass development and school terminations. Research by Nicola et al. (2020) and UNESCO (2020) have revealed that more than 1,576, 021, 858 (91.3%) of students worldwide have been deterred from completion. Wu et al (2010) revealed that the effects were not restricted to students alone but had far-reaching implications for other sectors of the economy. Hence, the need for urgent attention to curb the epidemic and reopen schools became imperative by all including Kogi state. According to Crawford et al. (2020), proactive endeavors concerning web-based learning have been set up in certain nations like Italy, Germany, Australia, Hong Kong, USA particularly nearby before the danger of the Coronavirus pandemic. Notwithstanding that, proof from writing portrays that the pandemic has applied sensible impacts to instruction in those regions of the planet (Crawford et al., 2020). In this manner, it is projected that the pandemic would have genuine intensification on schools, particularly in Nigeria which didn't take such instructive proactive measures, particularly internet learning stages preceding the pandemic (Zhong, 2020). The inability of the Nigerian government to take such proactive measures unlike the aforementioned countries was among the worrisome issues that motivated this research.

The effect of COVID-19 in low and medium-pay nations is especially startling to instruction to the degree that school systems have been dealing with unfortunate media (Adebayo, 2020). It is additionally noted to be challenging for these unfortunate nations to give the instructive necessities of their kin, particularly a safe learning climate for students (Zar et al., 2020). The diminished degree of training has been seen all over Nigeria and different nations throughout this pandemic which extends the current hole in learning access and results and expanded school quitters (Dorn et al., 2020). The level of school quitters orchestrated by the school shutdown as observed in Kogi state engendered this research.

The test presented to instruction in Nigeria is muddled because of impossible-to-miss weaknesses; including chronic frailty frameworks, neediness and imbalance, hunger, high populace, inside uprooted populace, metropolitan provincial flood, out-of-school populace, and high populace densities (Obiako and Adeniran, 2020). Preceding COVID-19, Nigeria represents one in every five of the world's out-of-younger students. Around 10.5 million young children 5 to 14 years in Nigeria were out of school and just around 61% of 6 to 11-year-old kids get grade school instruction consistently. Subsequently, while Nigeria is engaging with hidden instructive difficulties that have kept the country behind in preparing youngsters for the powerful work environment, COVID-19 effects further irritate this issue (Yinka and Adebayo, 2020). The observation has revealed that people were still engrossed with the fear of coronavirus infection in the aftermath of its menace and were holding back their wards from going to schools, especially public schools. This among other things motivates the researchers to investigate managerial strategies for students' safety in the post COVID-19 era in public secondary schools in Kogi state, Nigeria.

Information from researchers such as Eze et al (2021) revealed that all educational institutions in Nigeria were shut down from March 27, 2020, as one of the Federal Government's measures to reduce the spread of this lethal infection called the COVID-19 pandemic. This implies each school across the 36 states in the nation was shut down. Accordingly, different states' Ministries of Education have been delivering modalities for radio and TV tutoring and web-based learning for students in open essential and secondary schools. However, these endeavors could be powerful with experience from created nations, yet it prompted a broad adverse consequence on the school system in growing low-pay nations like Nigeria (Obiako and Adeniran, 2020). For example, as the COVID-19 pandemic is advancing computerized and online instruction all around the world, essential and secondary school students in rustic and serve metropolitan networks are falling behind because of the absence of abilities and assets to adjust to the new learning medium. Furthermore, college students who might have the right stuff to embrace web-based acquiring are tested with unfortunate web organization and ceaseless blackout (Crawford et al., 2020, Zhong, 2020). Subsequently, getting the hang of utilizing radio, TV, and internet learning stage for essential and secondary students, virtual libraries and online classes in colleges is not viable for most Nigerian people group. Zhong (2020) has stated that underfunded organizations and socially burdened students have restricted admittance to innovation and the web as well as students' failure to amplify a web-based climate, subvert government reaction. This study intended to ascertain the required preventive facilities for students' safety by the school management team and whether they can be affordable for students from poor homes.

The effects of school conclusion as brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic are probably going to expand the space in the norm of instruction and like financial exercises in the country. Just a lesser level of students who are from privileged foundations, particularly in the metropolitan regions, have more opportunities to get training during such school conclusion through innovation (Obiako and Adeniran, 2020), leaving behind by far most students from less privileged poor and underserved provincial and rural regions in the nation (Zhong, 2020). Leung and Sharma (2020) opined that aside from that, students whose schools come up short on assets or ability to adjust to this original conveyance are as of now missing learning. Great attrition of both students and staff in schools was observed by the researchers in Kogi state and one wonder whether this missing links could be recovered within

short time. Also, the internally generated revenue of the school was nothing to write home about which was among the problems observed to be encountered by the management of schools in Kogi state in the aftermath of COVID-19 pandemic.

Much exertion has been set up worldwide by both government and people to save what is going on. In Nigeria to be exact, prohibition on school conclusion was steadily eliminated by the administrative and a few state governments for individuals returning to schools with specific conditions, particularly in certain states where the impact/threat of Coronavirus is lesser. This severe experience of school conclusion and conditions for school returning doesn't extra school the executives across the instructive foundations as they also were burdened with the obligation of students' security in the Coronavirus period. A fundamental plan must be made for students' resumption particularly in the arrangement of more homerooms to get together the space expected by the national government and different things, for example, arrangement of facemasks, sanitizer, water, fumigants, chloride, hand globes, and so on notwithstanding gnawing economy. School the board similarly experienced despite everything encountering an exceptional decrease in students' enrolment in post-Coronavirus time with additional staggering impacts on private partners in training. A few difficulties, for example, lack of assets to buy the expected well-being materials, Attrition of students' enrolment, Attrition of staff in schools, Shortage of study halls and furniture to keep up with the suggested space, and Indiscriminate gathering of Covid-19 palliatives to schools were capable by the greater part of the schools in the perception of the specialists. This makes it undeniably challenging for a significant number of them to adapt to the school resumption strategy established by the public authority and parts more. In any case, the reason for the concern in this study is the managerial strategies for students' well-being in the aftermath of the Covid-19 pandemic in Kogi state that is yet to be known.

A few techniques were prescribed to be embraced by the school board for students' well-being for returning to schools the consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic by the Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC) (NCDC, 2020); World Health Organization (WHO, 2020b); Nigeria Education in Emergencies Working Group (2020) and Federal Ministry of Education (2020). A portion of the actions incorporate the accompanying:

1. Disinfect the school premises intermittently, particularly during school excursions: In request to control the spread of this infection and other infectious illnesses, the board of schools is encouraged to treat their schools' premises which will ultimately choke out irritations ridiculously also the infection. This will likewise kill a few toxic bugs and irritations that could have hurt students in their homeroom regions and quarters.
2. Arrangement of well-being and security faculty: To stay away from the local area spread of the sickness inside the school, it is fitting that the well-being and well-being workforce ought to be locked in promptly to deal with the logical instances of this pandemic that might come up. These schools fill in as a connection point between the students' populace and the school board for viable control of the sickness inside the school region.
3. Arrangement of the clinical report: It becomes essential for the administration of schools to be aware of everything about the well-being status of their students as it will assist them with dealing with a crisis case that might emerge all the more, so the COVID-19 pandemic is attacking. The administration is committed to

demanding their students give their clinical reports from perceived well-being offices for record purposes (Nigeria Education in Emergencies Working Group, 2020).

4. Diminish screen time: The school executives ought to lessen screen time for their students to keep away from advanced eye strain, which could prompt consuming, bothersome, or tired eyes, migraines, weakness, obscured or twofold vision, loss of concentration, neck torment and different dangers for youngsters utilizing screens time after time and excessively lengthy. Thus, schools ought to screen the time students spend on the screen. Screen time can be decreased by drawing in students in other fun exercises that don't need a screen to students (Federal Ministry of Education, 2020).
5. Ordinary check and upkeep of a perilous region: School administrations must be aware of risky regions and make vital fixes right away. For instance, assuming there are potholes in the school jungle gym or a homeroom entryway that hammers, the class instructor or cleaner ought to put those fixes at the first spot on her list. Moreover, ordinary assessments of jungle gym gear and offices ought to be led by school well-being and security agents and fixes of any messed-up hardware or perilous regions ought to be finished with prompt impact. The administration can make it a month-to-month schedule for an intensive check which will include each partner. For instance, assuming a piece of jungle gym hardware keeps on breaking, eliminate the whole piece of jungle gym gear (WHO, 2020a).
6. Utilitarian sickbay in school: To reduce non-appearance coming about because of minor well-being challenges, schools ought to guarantee that there is accessibility of sickbays inside the premises. This well-being office ought to be exceptional to deal with minor sicknesses and key well-being assets, for example, the medical aid box ought to be promptly accessible to offer help for harmed students or students showing side effects of an ailment that has been created while in school. Schools' ought to likewise be enlisted with any suitable medical clinic that could fill in as a reference community for debilitated students from the wiped-out sound to help the well-being arrangement of the school (WHO, 2020a).

Notwithstanding the abovementioned, the Federal Government of Nigeria in her bid for the great soundness of her residents expressed that the accompanying advances and moves should be made in schools in the wake of returning to somewhere safe and the prosperity of students, educators, managers, and another instruction workforce.

Sharpening: Every partner in the school ought to be appropriately educated about the illness, the method of transmission, and how ought to be overseen it. Furthermore, the government has taken liability for giving IEC materials including age-proper, comprehensive, Risk Communication and Community Engagement (RCCE) messages on school well-being to students, instructors, executives, and school networks (NCDC, 2020).

Security and Hygiene: There ought to be an elevated degree of consistency with NCDC rules and recommended well-being measures and practices, for example, normal check and actual assessment at school doors, sports, and extracurricular exercises, obligatory utilization of facial coverings, and hand washing offices in schools and during travel to and from schools. Sanitizers, cleanser and water are to be made available for students. Staff and guests to wash their hands before entering the school premises. Nose mask should be worn by guaranteed students,

instructors, executives, and other schooling staff while they are anywhere nearby. There should be tenacious temperature checks with non-contact thermometers at school passageways for all staff, students, and guests. Persistently fortify the school COVID-19 Referral System and empower and guarantee legitimate viable use. Move illustrations outside or cross-ventilate rooms however much as could reasonably be expected. Screen, track progress, and give criticism in understanding the M and E structure for safe school resuming (NCDC, 2020).

Social Protection: Ensure framework/methods for standard hand washing and sanitizer offices at basic places, cleaning and sterilization of basic spots/objects of high gamble openness, for example, handrails, work areas, play gear, book covers, and so on Lay out a clear direction and circle back to who is answerable for observing generally wellbeing and wellbeing estimates founded in schools and guaranteeing nonstop report. Guarantee food overseers and sellers are checked to deliver school supper administrations. Complete routine clean review of premises by EHOs. Create and carry out, where important, a choice model for reclosing and returning schools if there should be an occurrence of the resurgence of local area transmission (Nigeria Education in Emergencies Working Group, 2020). These procedures were tried to discover the level of their execution by the school executives in this review (NCDC, 2020; WHO, 2020a).

Strategies to be put in place for students' safety in post COVID-19 period have become worrisome nightmare for the secondary school management for most part of Nigeria and Kogi state. Measures, for example, wearing of facial covering, social distancing, aversion of handshaking, successive washing of hands, standard sharpening, and the utilization of hand sanitizer, among others were set up by the public authority. However, perceptions by analysts show that these actions were not as expected kept up with by certain schools in Nigeria particularly those schools in the provincial regions due to their non-trust in the threat of the Coronavirus pandemic. Issues, for example, scarcity of assets for the acquirement of Coronavirus, decrease of students' enrolment, and deficiency of study halls and furniture to keep up with the prescribed space were seen to be experienced in the administration of students' well-being in post Coronavirus period in most of the schools in Nigeria. In any case, the unmistakable proof is yet to show if such issues were experienced by the administration of public secondary schools in Kogi state. A few procedures, for example, the building of palliatives for the school executives, execution of social distancing, wearing of facemasks, implementation of incessant washing of hands, use of hand sanitizer, the utilization of non-contact thermometer to check the temperature of each section were seen to be embraced by the administration of schools for students' security in Nigeria. In any case, no realized work has shown that the administration of government-funded schools in Kogi state has taken on such techniques in the administration of students' security during the Coronavirus period. There is hence the earnest need to investigate managerial strategies for students' safety in the aftermath of COVID-19 in public secondary schools in Kogi state, Nigeria.

1.2. Purpose of The Study

The general purpose of the study was to determine managerial strategies for students' safety in the COVID-19 era in public secondary schools in Kogi State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the facilities required for students' safety in post- COVID-19 era in public secondary schools in Kogi state.
2. Ascertain the problems experienced in the administration of public secondary schools for students' safety during the aftermath of Coronavirus period
3. Ascertain the strategies to be embraced in the administration of public secondary schools for students' safety in post-Coronavirus time.

1.3. Research Questions

The accompanying examination questions directed the review:

1. What are the facilities required for students' safety during the post Coronavirus period?
2. What are the problems experienced in the administration of public secondary schools for students' well-being in post-Coronavirus time?
3. What are the strategies to be embraced in the administration of public secondary schools for students' safety in post-Coronavirus time?

2. Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design and utilized quantitative methodology for the collection of primary data. A descriptive survey as indicated by Omachi (2021a) portrays the traits of the populace or peculiarity considered. It centers on "what the future holds" for the examination subjects. It is legitimate because it is the motivation behind the review which is to explore administrative techniques for public secondary school students' safety in the Coronavirus period in Kogi state and data are required from directors of schools. Descriptive design is often used when research needs to examine current phenomena (Omachi, 2021a). The choice of the descriptive survey is appropriate because the topic under investigation aims at identifying characteristics, frequencies, trends, and categories of groups of individuals (school management team) who are involved in protection of students to enhance their safety in the post COVID-19 periods. The use of descriptive survey is also justified because not much is known yet about the school management team involvement in protection of students for safety in the aftermath of COVID-19 era in Kogi state, Nigeria. The choice of quantitative methodology for this study was justified because it allows for a broader study of this kind, involving a greater number of subjects, and enhancing the generalization of the results.

The review was done in Kogi State. Kogi state is comprised of 21 Local Government Areas. Kogi State was picked for this exploration due to the apparent unfortunate reaction to the Coronavirus pandemic sustained by the government during the period. The study covered the entire public secondary schools in Kogi state. Kogi State has 214 public secondary schools based on the information from the State Ministry of Education Office, Lokoja (2019). The number of respondents in this review comprised 214 principals from 214 public secondary schools in Kogi state. The sample for the review is comprised of 214 (100 percent) administrators from secondary schools who were selected using total enumeration technique of purposive sampling. The decision of 100 percent was an

assessment of Omachi (2021b) who thought that a 100% agent test of a populace of 200-500 is viewed as great. The choice of this population and sample was based on the fact that these subjects are the heads of these public schools and in the best position to supply the necessary information concerning the managerial strategies for students' safety in the post COVID-19 era in public secondary schools in Kogi state, Nigeria.

Coronavirus Protective Checklist (CPC) and Students' Safety in Post-Covid-19 Questionnaire (SSPCQ) were filled in as instruments for data collection. They were face-approved by 3 specialists from Educational Foundations and Measurement and Evaluation, Departments of Educational Foundations, Kogi State University, Anyigba. CPC contains a rundown of suggested Coronavirus defensive materials where the respondents (directors) were directed to tick Yes or No suitably. SSPCQ had two sections. Section A contains demographic characteristics of the respondents while Section B is clustered into A and B. Group A contains items on challenges facing school management in the course of providing students' security in post-coronavirus resumption of schools while Cluster B manages items on techniques to be taken on for dealing with students' security in public secondary schools.

CPC and SSPCQ preliminary tried utilizing twenty (20) private secondary school administrators (10 males and 10 females) in Kogi state in a place that is not part of the sample yet from the number of participants in the same qualities in the same Kogi State. CPC contains seven items of Yes or No. SSPCQ contained 10 items where respondents were guided by the four-point Likert scale with response mode of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. Kuder Richardson was utilized to compute the reactions of CPC and Cronbach's Alpha was utilized to work out the interior consistency SSPCQ on the SPSS, which yielded dependability co-productive files of 0.81 and 0.83. This demonstrates high inward consistency and dependability of the instrument for use (Omachi, 2021a). A reliability test was carried out because it confirms the consistency across the parts of a measuring instrument for this study.

The researchers controlled and gathered the data for the study for multiple weeks with the assistance of two research colleagues. For the data investigation, the basic rate was to utilize and answer research question one whose benchmark was put at 2.50 where beneath was intended for rejection and above to be accepted. Percentage, mean, and standard deviation were utilized to respond to the research questions that guided the study with a cut-off mark of 2.50.

3. Results and Discussions

This section deals with data presentation, analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings on managerial strategies for public secondary school students' safety in post COVID-19 era in Kogi state. The data that provide an answer to this research question is presented in table.

RQ1: What are the facilities required for students' safety in the post-COVID-19 eras?

Table 1. Percentage ratings of principals on facilities required for students’ safety in the aftermath of COVID-19

S/NO	Required Facilities for Students’ Safety in Post COVID-19	Yes	%	Decision	No	%	Decision
1	Android phones for online lessons	14	6.54	Very weak	200	93.46	Very strong
2	Steady water supply	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak
3	Hand sanitizer	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak
4	Face mask	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak
5	Soap	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak
6	Chlorine solution	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak
7	Separate toilet	116	54.20	Very strong	98	45.80	Weak
8	Fumigants	185	86.44	Very strong	29	13.56	Very weak
9	Hand globe	201	93.93	Very strong	13	6.07	Very weak
10	Thermometer	214	100	Very strong	0	0	Very weak

N1=214 Principals

Table 1 above shows the percentage ratings of principals on required facilities for students’ safety in post COVID-19 era in schools. It showed that the number and percentage ratings by principals for items 1-10 were 14, 214, 214, 214, 214, 214, 116, 185, 201 and 214 with corresponding percentages to be 6.54%, 100%, 100%, 100%, 100%, 100%, 54.20%, 86.44%, 93.93% and 100% respectively. This means that the respondents almost agreed with the strong response that steady water supply, hand sanitizer, face mask, soap, chlorine solution, separate toilet, fumigants, hand globe and thermometer are the facilities required to steadily be in schools for students’ safety in post COVID-19 eras except item 1 which constitutes 14 respondents with the corresponding percentage of 6.54% that disagreed that much emphasis was not placed on android phone for online lessons among students in their safety maintenance.

RQ2: What are the problems encountered in the management of public secondary school students’ safety in the post-COVID-19 eras?

Table 2. Mean ratings and standard deviation of school management on problems encountered in the management of public secondary school students’ safety in the aftermath of COVID-19

Item No		SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	Std	Decision
1.	Paucity of funds to purchase the required safety materials.	152	58	1	3	3.67	1.91	Accepted
2.	Attrition of students’ enrolment.	175	37	1	1	3.80	1.94	Accepted
3.	Attrition of staff in schools	151	46	14	3	3.61	1.90	Accepted
4.	Shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space.	111	101	1	1	3.50	1.87	Accepted
5.	Indiscriminate accruing of COVID-19 palliatives to schools.	138	58	8	10	3.51	1.87	Accepted
Cluster means/standard deviation						3.62	1.90	Accepted

Source: Field work (2021)

Table 2 showed that the mean ratings for items 1-5 were 3.67, 3.80, 3.61, 3.50, and 3.51 respectively with corresponding standard deviations of 1.91, 1.94, 1.90, 1.87, and 1.87. All the means ratings are above the cut-off point of 2:50. This means that the respondents had agreed that school management encountered such problems as a Paucity of funds to purchase the required safety materials, Attrition of students’ enrolment, Attrition of staff in schools, Shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space and Indiscriminate accruing of COVID-19 palliatives to schools in the management of public secondary school students’ safety in post COVID-19 era.

RQ3: Strategies to be adopted in the management of public secondary school students' safety in the post COVID-19 era?

Table 3. Mean ratings and standard deviations of school management on strategies adopted in the management of public secondary school students' safety in the aftermath of COVID-19

Item No		SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	Std	Decision
1.	Physical/social distancing for prevention of COVID19 infections.	152	56	2	4	3.70	1.92	Accepted
2.	Implementation of NCC guidelines and prescribed safety measures and practices, such as proper screening at school entrances, sports and extracurricular activities, use of face masks, diligent temperature checks with non-contact thermometers at school entrances for all staff, learners, and visitors	162	49	1	2	3.73	1.93	Accepted
3.	Cleaning and disinfection of critical places/objects of high risk, expose, such as handrails, desks, play equipment, book covers.	130	82	1	1	3.60	1.89	Accepted
4.	Appoint trained health and safety officials.	111	101	1	1	3.50	1.87	Accepted
5.	Accruing of palliatives to the school management to solve the problem of funding.	131	80	1	2	3.59	1.89	Accepted
Cluster means/standard deviation						3.62	1.90	Accepted

Source: Field work (2021)

Table 3 showed that the mean ratings for items 1 – 5 were 3.70, 3.73, 3.60, 3.50, and 3.59 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.92, 1.93, 1.89, 1.87 and 1.89. All the means were higher than the cut-off mark of 2.50 which indicated that all the items were accepted as strategies adopted by management of public secondary school for students' safety in post-Covid-19 era in Kogi state.

Based on the analysis of the three research questions, the following findings are organized and discussed here for ease of understanding:

The first finding of this study revealed that a steady water supply, hand sanitizer, face mask, soap, chlorine solution, separate toilet, fumigants, hand globe and non-contact thermometers are the facilities required to steadily be in schools for students' safety in post-COVID-19 eras except item 1 which constitutes 14 respondents with the corresponding percentage of 6.54% that disagreed that much emphasis was not placed on android phone for online lessons among students in their safety maintenance. In a similar view, the Federal Ministry of Education (2020) in her guidelines for schools and learning facilities reopening after COVID-19 pandemic closures recommended such facilities as water, hand sanitizer, face mask, soap, chlorine solution, separate toilets, fumigants, hand globe and non-contact thermometer to steadily be in schools for students' safety in post-COVID-19 era.

The second finding of this study revealed that school management encountered such problems as the paucity of funds to purchase the required safety materials, attrition of students' enrolment, Attrition of staff in schools, Shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space and Indiscriminate accruing of COVID-19 palliatives to schools in the management of public secondary school students' safety in post COVID-19 era. This finding is consistent with the view of Eze, Sefotho, Onyishi & Eseadi (2021) that the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic does not spare school management as attrition of both students and staff has been noticed in the schools.

The third finding of this study revealed that physical/social distancing, Implementation of NCDC guidelines and prescribed safety measures and practices, such as proper screening at school entrances, sports, and extra-curricular activities, use of face masks, diligent temperature checks with non-contact thermometers at school entrances for all staff, learners, and visitors. Cleaning and disinfection of critical places/objects of high-risk exposure such as handrails, desks, play equipment, and book covers, appoint trained health and safety officials, and Accruing palliatives to the school management are strategies adopted by school management of the public secondary school for students' safety in post COVID-19 era in the schools. This finding is in line with the recommendations of the NCDC (2020), WHO (2020b), and Nigeria Education in Emergencies Working Group (2020) that the use of face masks, diligent temperature checks with non-contact thermometers at school entrances for all staff, learners and visitors should be prioritized. They also published that proper screening at school entrances, sports, and extra-curricular activities including the cleansing and disinfection of critical places/objects of high-risk exposure such as handrails, desks, play equipment, book covers must always be carried out on the routine basis by the school administrators in the schools during the reopening of schools.

4. Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concluded that problems such as paucity of funds for the procurement of aids, reduction of students' enrolment, and shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space were encountered in the management of students' safety in post COVID-19 era by the school management in Kogi state. Some strategies such as accruing of palliatives to the school management, implementation of social distancing, wearing of facemasks, enforcement of frequent washing of hands, application of hand sanitizer, the use of a non-contact thermometer to check the temperature of every entry was to be adopted by the management of schools for students' safety in Kogi state in post COVID-19 era though much efforts are still required from the government to sensitize the patronage of schools in the rural communities about the menace and reality of COVID-19 pandemic in the state.

4.1 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Efforts should be made by the government to sensitize rural dwellers about the danger of COVID-19 pandemic. This will assist them to adhere strictly to the Covid protocols for their safety in schools.
2. Reasonable palliatives should be given to school management to ease their purchase of the recommended protective COVID-19 facilities for students' safety in their schools. This will strengthen the management in the full implementation of COVID-19 protocols for students' safety in schools.
3. The building of more classroom blocks should be sponsored by the government in public schools. This will assist the schools' management to maintain the recommended classroom space by the government in the aftermath of COVID-19 for students' safety.

4.2. Implications of the Study to Education and Society

The findings of this study have far-reaching implications for education and for a larger society. Some of the implications are as follows:

The first finding revealed that a steady water supply, hand sanitizer, face mask, soap, chlorine solution, separate toilet, fumigants, hand globe, and non-contact thermometer are the facilities required to steadily be in schools for students' safety in post COVID-19 era. This implies that school management should as a matter of necessity provide the above items for the sureness of students' safety in their schools if they must reopen normal activities. These findings imply that many schools in the rural environment will not be able to reopen academic activities partly due to the usual poor attention of the government on schools in the rural environment of Nigeria. Besides, the rigorous procedures to get such preventive items from the government are cumbersome and discouraging due to the stringent conditionality attached to the collection.

The finding equally revealed that school management encountered such problems as the paucity of funds to purchase the required safety materials, attrition of students' enrolment, attrition of staff in schools, shortage of classrooms and furniture to maintain the recommended space, and indiscriminate accruing of COVID-19 palliatives to schools for the management of public secondary school students' safety in post COVID-19 era. This implies that school management especially those in the rural environment are not given due assistance for the effective running of the schools and this may affect their financial buoyancy to meet up with prescribed measures by the government. The implication of this finding is apparent in the unprecedented attrition of both staff and student enrolment in their schools in the post-Covid-19 era in Nigeria. The situation was so sympathetic in the rural environment as many schools struggled with reopening due to a lack of money by the head teachers at the primary and secondary levels in the rural schools resulting in a bigger gap in educational attainment between rural dwellers and urban settlers in Nigeria.

The finding of the study also revealed that physical/social distancing, implementation of NCDC guidelines and prescribed safety measures and practices, such as proper screening at school entrances, sports, and extra-curricular activities, including the use of face masks, diligent temperature checks with non-contact thermometers at school entrances for all staff, learners, and visitors are strategies to be adopted by school management for students' safety during school reopening in post COVID-19. Cleaning and disinfection of critical places/objects of high-risk exposure such as handrails, desks, play equipment, and book covers, appointing trained health and safety officials, and accruing palliatives to the school management were also strategies adopted by school management of the public secondary school for students' safety in post COVID-19 era in the schools. This implies that for assurance of students' safety in schools, the above items as recommended must be put in place in every school in Nigeria irrespective of their location. But unfortunately, the recommendations were only seen on papers and other social media such as radio and television, and not seen in the practical situation of the beneficiary in Nigeria. This finding implies that many lives were claimed by the pandemic and some schools could not resume on time especially those in rural environments which creates educational inequality in Nigeria.

Declaration of Competing Interest and Ethics

The authors declare no conflict of interest. This research study complies with research publishing ethics. The scientific and legal responsibility for this manuscript published in OPS Journal belongs to the authors.

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